

Two conjectures about strobogrammatic numbers

Conjecture 1. There are infinitely many strobogrammatic numbers, that are also prime numbers.

Conjecture 2. There are infinitely many strobogrammatic numbers, that are also Sophie Germain prime numbers.

Note 1. A strobogrammatic numbers is a number whose numeral is rotationally symmetric, so that it appears the same when rotated 180 degrees.

Note 2. A Sophie Germain prime number is a prime number p such that $2p+1$ is also a prime number.